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UTILIZING IMBALANCED DATA AND CLASSIFICATION COST MATRIX TO PREDICT MOVIE PREFERENCES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a movie genre recommendation system based on imbalanced survey data and unequal classification costs for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) who need a data-based and analytical approach to stock favored movies and target marketing to young people. The dataset maintains a detailed personal profile as predictors including demographic, behavioral and preferences information for each user as well as imbalanced genre preferences. These predictors do not include movies' information such as actors or directors. The paper applies Gentle boost, Adaboost and Bagged tree ensembles as well as SVM machine learning algorithms to learn classification from one thousand observations and predict movie genre preferences with adjusted classification costs. The proposed recommendation system also selects important predictors to avoid overfitting and to shorten training time. This paper compares the test error among the above-mentioned algorithms that are used to recommend different movie genres. The prediction power is also indicated in a comparison of precision and recall with other state-of-the-art recommendation systems. The proposed movie genre recommendation system solves problems such as small dataset, imbalanced response, and unequal classification costs.

KEYWORDS

Machine learning; Classification; Recommendation system.

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REGULARIZED FUZZY NEURAL NETWORKS TO AID EFFORT FORECASTING IN THE CONSTRUCTION AND SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Predicting the time to build software is a very complex task for software engineering managers. There are complex factors that can directly interfere with the productivity of the development team. Factors directly related to the complexity of the system to be developed drastically change the time necessary for the completion of the works with the software factories. This work proposes the use of a hybrid system based on artificial neural networks and fuzzy systems to assist in the construction of an expert system based on rules to support in the prediction of hours destined to the development of software according to the complexity of the elements present in the same. The set of fuzzy rules obtained by the system helps the management and control of software development by providing a base of interpretable estimates based on fuzzy rules. The model was submitted to tests on a real database, and its results were promissory in the construction of an aid mechanism in the predictability of the software construction.

KEYWORDS

Fuzzy neural networks, effort forecasting, use case point, expert systems.

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**NETWORK LEARNING AND TRAINING OF A CASCADED LINK-BASED
FEED FORWARD NEURAL NETWORK (CLBFFNN) IN AN
INTELLIGENT TRIMODAL BIOMETRIC SYSTEM**

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ABSTRACT

Presently, considering the technological advancement of our modern world, we are in dire need for a system that can learn new concepts and give decisions on its own. Hence the Artificial Neural Network is all that is required in the contemporary situation. In this paper, CLBFFNN is presented as a special and intelligent form of artificial neural networks that has the capability to adapt to training and learning of new ideas and be able to give decisions in a trimodal biometric system involving fingerprints, face and iris biometric data. It gives an overview of neural networks.

KEYWORDS

CLBFFNN, Learning, Training, Artificial Neural Network, Trimodal, Biometric System

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